

On a Deconcatenation Problem

Henry Ibstedt

Abstract: In a recent study of the *Primality of the Smarandache Symmetric Sequences* Sabin and Tatiana Tabirca [1] observed a very high frequency of the prime factor 333667 in the factorization of the terms of the second order sequence. The question if this prime factor occurs periodically was raised. The odd behaviour of this and a few other primefactors of this sequence will be explained and details of the periodic occurrence of this and of several other prime factors will be given.

Definition: The n th term of the Smarandache symmetric sequence of the second order is defined by $S(n)=123\dots n_n\dots 321$ which is to be understood as a concatenation¹ of the first n natural numbers concatenated with a concatenation in reverse order of the n first natural numbers.

Factorization and Patterns of Divisibility

The first five terms of the sequence are: 11, 1221, 123321, 12344321, 1234554321. The number of digits $D(n)$ of $S(n)$ is growing rapidly. It can be found from the formula:

$$D(n) = 2k(n+1) - \frac{2(10^k - 1)}{9} \text{ for } n \text{ in the interval } 10^{k-1} \leq n < 10^k - 1 \quad (1)$$

In order to study the repeated occurrence of certain prime factors the table of $S(n)$ for $n \leq 100$ produced in [1] has been extended to $n \leq 200$. Tabirca's aim was to factorize the terms $S(n)$ as far as possible which is more ambitious than the aim of the present calculation which is to find prime factors which are less than 10^8 . The result is shown in table 1.

The computer file containing table 1 is analysed in various ways. Of the 664579 primes which are smaller than 10^7 only 192 occur in the prime factorizations of $S(n)$ for $1 \leq n \leq 200$. Of these 192 primes 37 occur more than once. The record holder is 333667, the 28693th prime, which occurs 45 times for $1 \leq n \leq 200$ while its neighbours 333647 and 333673 do not even occur once. Obviously there is something to be explained here. The frequency of the most frequently occurring primes is shown below..

Table 2. Most frequently occurring primes

p	3	333667	37	41	271	9091	11	43	73	53	97	31	47
Freq	132	45	41	41	41	29	25	24	14	8	7	6	6

¹ In this article the concatenation of a and b is written a_b . Multiplication ab is often made explicit by writing $a.b$. When there is no reason for misunderstanding the signs “ $_$ ” and “ \cdot ” are omitted. Several tables contain prime factorizations. Prime factors are given in ascending order, multiplication is expressed by “ \cdot ” and the last factor is followed by “ \dots ” if the factorization is incomplete or by $Fxxx$ indicating the number of digits of the last factor. To avoid typing errors all tables are electronically transferred from the calculation program, which is DOS-based, to the wordprocessor. All editing has been done either with a spreadsheet program or directly with the text editor. Full page tables have been placed at the end of the article. A non-proportional font has been used to illustrate the placement of digits when this has been found useful.

The distribution of the primes 11, 37, 41, 43, 271, 9091 and 333667 is shown in table 3. It is seen that the occurrence patterns are different in the intervals $1 \leq n \leq 9$, $10 \leq n \leq 99$ and $100 \leq n \leq 200$. Indeed the last interval is part of the interval $100 \leq n \leq 999$. It would have been very interesting to include part of the interval $1000 \leq n \leq 9999$ but as we can see from (1) already $S(1000)$ has 5786 digits. Partition lines are drawn in the table to highlight the different intervals. The less frequent primes are listed in table 4 where primes occurring more than once are partitioned.

From the patterns in table 3 we can formulate the occurrence of these primes in the intervals $1 \leq n \leq 9$, $10 \leq n \leq 99$ and $100 \leq n \leq 200$, where the formulas for the last interval are indicative. We note, for example, that 11 is not a factor of any term in the interval $100 \leq n \leq 999$. This indicates that the divisibility patterns for the interval $1000 \leq n \leq 9999$ and further intervals is a completely open question.

Table 5 shows an analysis of the patterns of occurrence of the primes in table 1 by interval. Note that we only have observations up to $n=200$. Nevertheless the interval $100 \leq n \leq 999$ is used. This will be justified in the further analysis.

Table 5. Divisibility patterns

Interval	p	n	Range for j
$1 \leq n \leq 9$	3	$2+3j$	$j=0, 1, \dots$
$10 \leq n \leq 99$		$3j$	$j=1, 2, \dots$
$1 \leq n \leq 9$	11	All values of n	
$10 \leq n \leq 99$		$12+11j$	$j=0, 1, \dots, 7$
$100 \leq n \leq 999$		$20+11j$ None	$j=0, 1, \dots, 7$
$1 \leq n \leq 9$	37	$2+3j$	$j=0, 1, 2$
$10 \leq n \leq 99$		$3+3j$	$j=0, 1, 2$
$100 \leq n \leq 999$		$12+3j$	$j=0, 1, \dots, 28, 29$
		$122+37j$ $136+37j$	$j=0, 1, \dots, 23$ $j=0, 1, \dots, 23$
$1 \leq n \leq 9$	41	$4+5j$	$j=0, 1$
$10 \leq n \leq 999$		5 $14+5j$	$j=0, 1, \dots, 197$
$1 \leq n \leq 9$	43	None	
$10 \leq n \leq 99$		$11+21j$	$j=0, 1, 3, 4$
$100 \leq n \leq 999$		$24+21j$ 100	$j=0, 1, 2, 3$
		$107+7j$	$j=0, 1, \dots, 127$
$1 \leq n \leq 9$	271	$4+5j$	$j=0, 1$
$10 \leq n \leq 999$		5 $14+5j$	$j=0, 1, \dots, 197$
$1 \leq n \leq 999$	9091	$9+5j$	$j=0, 1, \dots, 98$
$1 \leq n \leq 9$	333667	8, 9	
$10 \leq n \leq 99$		$18+9j$	$j=0, 1, \dots, 9$
$100 \leq n \leq 999$		$102+3j$	$j=0, 1, \dots, 299$

We note that no terms are divisible by 11 for $n > 100$ in the interval $100 \leq n \leq 200$ and that no term is divisible by 43 in the interval $1 \leq n \leq 9$. Another remarkable observation is that the sequence shows exactly the same behaviour for the primes 41 and 271 in the intervals included in the study. Will they show the same behaviour when $n \geq 1000$?

Consider

$$S(n)=12\dots n_n\dots 21.$$

Let p be a divisor of $S(n)$. We will construct a number

$$N=12\dots n_0_0_n\dots 21 \tag{2}$$

so that p also divides N . What will be the number of zeros? Before discussing this let's consider the case $p=3$.

Case 1. $p=3$.

In the case $p=3$ we use the familiar rule that a number is divisible by 3 if and only if its digit sum is divisible by 3. In this case we can insert as many zeros as we like in (2) since this does not change the sum of digits. We also note that any integer formed by concatenation of three consecutive integers is divisible by 3, cf a_a+1_a+2 , digit sum $3a+3$. It follows that also $a_a+1_a+2_a+2_a+1_a$ is divisible by 3. For $a=n+1$ we insert this instead of the appropriate number of zeros in (2). This means that if $S(n)\equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ then $S(n+3)\equiv 0 \pmod{3}$. We have seen that $S(2)\equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ and $S(3)\equiv 0 \pmod{3}$. By induction it follows that $S(2+3j)\equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ for $j=1,2,\dots$ and $S(3j)\equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ for $j=1,2,\dots$.

We now return to the general case. $S(n)$ is deconcatenated into two numbers $12\dots n$ and $n\dots 21$ from which we form the numbers

$$A = 12\dots n \cdot 10^{1+\lceil \log_{10} B \rceil} \text{ and } B = n\dots 21$$

We note that this is a different way of writing $S(n)$ since indeed $A+B=S(n)$ and that $A+B\equiv 0 \pmod{p}$. We now form $M=A\cdot 10^s+B$ where we want to determine s so that $M\equiv 0 \pmod{p}$. We write M in the form $M=A(10^s-1)+A+B$ where $A+B$ can be ignored mod p . We exclude the possibility $A\equiv 0 \pmod{p}$ which is not interesting. This leaves us with the congruence

$$M\equiv A(10^s-1)\equiv 0 \pmod{p}$$

or

$$10^s-1\equiv 0 \pmod{p}$$

We are particularly interested in solutions for which

$$p \in \{1, 37, 41, 43, 271, 9091, 333667\}$$

By the nature of the problem these solutions are periodic. Only the two first values of s are given for each prime.

Table 6. $10^s-1\equiv 0 \pmod{p}$

p	3	11	37	41	43	271	9091	33367
s	1, 2	2, 4	3, 6	5, 10	21, 42	5, 10	10, 20	9, 18

We note that the result is independent of n . This means that we can use n as a parameter when searching for a sequence $C=n+1_n+2_ \dots n+k_n+k_ \dots n+2_n+1$ such that this is also divisible by p and hence can be inserted in place of the zeros to form $S(n+k)$ which then fills the condition $S(n+k)\equiv 0 \pmod{p}$. Here k is a multiple of s or $s/2$ in case s is even. This explains the results which we have already obtained in a different way as part of the factorization of $S(n)$ for $n\leq 200$, see tables 3 and 5. It remains to explain the periodicity which as we have seen is different in different intervals $10^u\leq n\leq 10^u-1$.

Condition 2. There must exist a term $S(n)$ with $n \geq 1000$ divisible by 333667 which will constitute the first term of the sequence.

The last term for $n < 1000$ which is divisible by 333667 is $S(999)$ from which we build

$$S(108) = 12_999_1000_ _1008_1008_ _1000_999_ _21$$

where we deconcatenate 100010011002...10081008...10011000 which is divisible by 333667 and provides the C-term (as introduced in the case studies) needed to generate the sequence, i.e. condition 2 is met.

We conclude that $S(1008+9j) \equiv 0 \pmod{333667}$ for $j=0,1,2, \dots, 999$. The last term in this sequence is $S(9999)$. From table 7 we see that there could be a sequence with the period 9 in the interval $10000 \leq n \leq 99999$ and a sequence with period 3 in the interval $100000 \leq n \leq 999999$. It is not difficult to verify that the above conditions are filled also in these intervals. This means that we have:

$$\begin{array}{ll} S(1008+9j) \equiv 0 \pmod{333667} & \text{for } j=0,1,2,\dots,999, \text{ i.e. } 10^3 \leq n \leq 10^4 - 1 \\ S(10008+9j) \equiv 0 \pmod{333667} & \text{for } j=0,1,2,\dots,9999, \text{ i.e. } 10^4 \leq n \leq 10^5 - 1 \\ S(100002+3j) \equiv 0 \pmod{333667} & \text{for } j=0,1,2,\dots,99999, \text{ i.e. } 10^5 \leq n \leq 10^6 - 1 \end{array}$$

It is one of the fascinations with large numbers to find such properties. This extraordinary property of the prime 333667 in relation to the Smarandache symmetric sequence probably holds for $n > 10^6$. It is easy to lose contact with reality when playing with numbers like this. We have $S(999999) \equiv 0 \pmod{333667}$. What does this number $S(999999)$ look like? Applying (1) we find that the number of digits $D(999999)$ of $S(999999)$ is

$$D(999999) = 2 \cdot 6 \cdot 10^6 - 2 \cdot (10^6 - 1) / 9 = 11777778$$

Let's write this number with 80 digits per line, 60 lines per page, using both sides of the paper. We will need 1226 sheets of paper – more than 2 reams!

Question 2. Why is there no sequence of $S(n)$ divisible by 11 in the interval $100 \leq n \leq 999$?

Condition 1. We must have a sequence of the form 100100... divisible by 11 to ensure the periodicity. As we can see from table 7 the sequence 100100 fills the condition and we would have a periodicity equal to 2 if the next condition is met.

Condition 2. There must exist a term $S(n)$ with $n \geq 100$ divisible by 11 which would constitute the first term of the sequence. This time let's use a nice property of the prime 11:

$$10^s \equiv (-1)^s \pmod{11}$$

Let's deconcatenate the number a_b corresponding to the concatenation of the numbers a and b : We have:

$$a_b = a \cdot 10^{1+\lfloor \log_{10} b \rfloor} + b = \begin{cases} -a+b & \text{if } 1+\lfloor \log_{10} b \rfloor \text{ is odd} \\ a+b & \text{if } 1+\lfloor \log_{10} b \rfloor \text{ is even} \end{cases}$$

Let's first consider a deconcatenated middle part of $S(n)$ where the concatenation is done with three-digit integers. For convenience I have chosen a concrete example – the generalization should pose no problem

$$273274275275274273 \equiv 2-7+3-2+7-4+2-7+5-2+7-5+2-7+4-2+7-3 \equiv 0 \pmod{11}$$

+--+--+--+--+--+--+--+

It is easy to see that this property holds independent of the length of the sequence above and whether it start on + or -. It is also easy to understand that equivalent results are obtained for other primes although factors other than +1 and -1 will enter into the picture.

We now return to the question of finding the first term of the sequence. We must start from $n=97$ since $S(97)$ is the last term for which we know that $S(n) \equiv 0 \pmod{11}$. We form:

$$9899100101 \dots n \dots 1011009998 \equiv 2 \pmod{11} \text{ independent of } n < 1000.$$

+--+--+--+--+ _ ---+--+--+--+

This means that $S(n) \equiv 2 \pmod{11}$ for $100 \leq n \leq 999$ and explains why there is no sequence divisible by 11 in this interval.

Question 3. Will there be a sequence divisible by 11 in the interval $1000 \leq n \leq 9999$?

Condition 1. A sequence 10001000...1000 divisible by 11 exists and would provide a period of 11, see table 7.

Condition 2. We need to find one value $n \geq 1000$ for which $S(n) \equiv 0 \pmod{11}$. We have seen that $S(999) \equiv 2 \pmod{11}$. We now look at the sequences following $S(999)$. Since $S(999) \equiv 2 \pmod{9}$ we need to insert a sequence $10001001 \dots m \dots 10011000 \equiv 9 \pmod{11}$ so that $S(m) \equiv 0 \pmod{11}$. Unfortunately m does not exist as we will see below

$$10001000 \equiv 2 \pmod{11}$$

+--+--+--+

$$1 \quad 1$$

$$1000100110011000 \equiv 2 \pmod{11}$$

+--+--+--+--+--+--+

$$1 \quad 1 \quad 1 \quad 1$$

1 \quad 1

$$100010011002100210011000 \equiv 0 \pmod{11}$$

+--+--+--+--+--+--+--+

$$1 \quad 1 \quad 1 \quad 1 \quad 1 \quad 1$$

1 \quad 2 \quad 2 \quad 1

$$10001001100210031003100210011000 \equiv -4 \equiv 7 \pmod{11}$$

+--+--+--+--+--+--+--+--+

$$1 \quad 1 \quad 1 \quad 1 \quad 1 \quad 1 \quad 1 \quad 1$$

1 \quad 2 \quad 3 \quad 3 \quad 2 \quad 1

Continuing this way we find that the residues form the period 2,2,0,7,1,4,5,4,1,7,0. We needed a residue to be 9 in order to build sequences divisible by 9. We conclude that $S(n)$ is not divisible by 11 in the interval $1000 \leq n \leq 9999$.

Trying to do the above analysis with the computer programs used in the early part of this study causes overflow because the large integers involved. However, changing the approach and performing calculations modulus 11 posed no problems. The above method was preferred for clarity of presentation.

Epilog

There are many other questions that may be interesting to look into. This is left to the reader. The author's main interest in this has been to develop means by which it is possible to identify some properties of large numbers other than the so frequently asked question as to whether a big number is a prime or not. There are two important ways to generate large numbers that I found particularly interesting – iteration and concatenation. In this article the author has drawn on work done previously, references below. In both these areas very large numbers may be generated for which it may be impossible to find any practical use – the methods are often more important than the results.

References:

1. Tabirca, S. and T., *On Primality of the Smarandache Symmetric Sequences*, Smarandache Notions Journal, Vol. 12, No 1-3 Spring 2001, 114-121.
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